

**Let the
dialogue
begin**

D2.3 DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF KNOWLEDGE EXCHANGE FORMATS

Project: **Cross-sector dialogue for Wildfire Risk Management**

Acronym: **Firelogue**

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
AB	Advisory Board
BG	Break-out Group
BoC	Board of Coordinators
CB	Communication Booster
DRMC	Disaster Risk Management Cycle
DG-ECHO	Directorate-General for European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations
EWE	Extreme Wildfires Events
Fire-In	Fire and Rescue Innovation Action
Firelinks	Fire in the Earth System: Science & Society
FIRE-RES	Innovative technologies and socio-ecological-economic solutions for fire resilient territories in Europe
FirEUrisk	Developing a holistic, risk-wise strategy for European wildfire management
GD-SO	Green Deal Projects Support Office
IA	Innovation Action
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
SAFERS	Structured approaches for forest fire emergencies in resilient societies
SILVANUS	Integrated Technological and Information Platform for wildfire Management
TREEADS ¹	A Holistic Fire Management Ecosystem for Prevention, Detection and Restoration of Environmental Disasters
WFRM	Wildfire Risk Management
WG	Working Group
Consortium partners	
ADAI	Association for the Development of Industrial Aerodynamics
CMCC	Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici
CTFC	Forest Science and Technology Centre of Catalonia
EDGE	EDGE in Earth Observation sciences Monoprosopi IKE
FhG	Fraunhofer Gesellschaft für Angewandte Forschung e.V.
IIASA	International Institute of Applied System Analysis
INESTEC	Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores, Tecnologia e Ciência
KEMEA	Centre for Security Studies
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
PCF	Pau Costa Foundation
SAFE	SAFE Cluster
TIEMS	The International Emergency Management Society
TRI	Trilateral Research
UAH	University of Alcalá
VOST	Virtual Operations Support Team from Portugal

¹ Previously named DRYADS

Executive Summary

The present deliverable is the first of a series of three deliverables targeted at the design of Knowledge Exchange Formats: D2.3, D2.8 and D2.9. The objective of this first deliverable D2.3 is to provide and define a set of Knowledge Exchange Formats as forms of cooperation, cross-fertilisation and networking among the EU fire projects from the Firelogue network. The strategy for their implementation implies the interaction with the EU fire projects that are part of the Firelogue network. For that, this document sets the framework to establish the communication with representatives of the EU fire projects holding responsibility in certain strategic/managerial areas (e.g., communication, research integration, impact assessment) and technical areas (e.g., ecology, societal aspects, infrastructures...), which is articulated by means of the Break-out Groups (BGs – strategic level) and the Working Groups (WGs – technical level), respectively.

All the Knowledge Exchange activities that will be carried out during Firelogue will be tracked in coordination with WP6 leaders (Dissemination and insight upscaling), who have already prepared a template to keep track of the communication and dissemination activities. An approximate timeline for the implementation of the Knowledge Exchange activities is drawn accounting for the planned and expected events organised by the projects themselves or by external parties. Finally, some contingency measures are foreseen to ensure appropriate engagement and successful implementation of the Knowledge Exchange activities.

1 Firelogue: promoting synergies for networking among the WFRM community

The Firelogue project has as a core objective the creation of a network for the discussion on the future of European Wildfire Risk Management (WFRM). This network provides support to the so-called EU fire projects by enabling synergies, coordinating efforts, and ultimately by maximising their impact. While Firelogue is primarily committed to the Green Deal (LC-GD-1-1) Innovation Actions (IAs henceforth), i.e., TREEADS [1], FIRE-RES [2], and SILVANUS [3], the network of EU fire projects has also extended this support to FirEURisk [4], SAFERS [5], Firelinks [6], Fire-In [7]. To a lesser extent, other projects from the WFRM domain have occasionally participated in some of the activities coordinated by Firelogue; namely, NEMAUSUS [8], Pyrolife [9] or AFAN [10].

Figure 1. EU fire projects within the Firelogue network.

The coordination role of Firelogue is the glue to ensure the cohesion bonds across the EU fire projects that are committed to enhance the status of WFRM from different disciplines, areas of expertise, and innovative approaches. Firelogue will enable communication spaces to share knowledge and scientific research, interaction with counterparts from other regions, as well as with decision makers entities at different managerial levels (i.e., strategic, tactical, operational) through formal capacity building. This will result in increased chances to empower key stakeholders from EU fire projects, leveraging their knowledge and capacities, as well as the tools and approaches developed in their respective projects.

The basis to perform that coordination is presented in this deliverable, which is aimed to formulate and classify the various Knowledge Exchange Formats in which the interaction among projects may occur. Not only these formats are here identified, but also the stakeholders that may be involved in each exchange format, considering the stakeholder clustering made in D7.2 [11]. This will help to better establish the framework for fluent and orderly communication with the EU fire projects to enhance the effectiveness of the coordination efforts.

1.1 Support Dimension

Firelogue establishes a Support Dimension that is designed to support the EU fire projects and additional WFRM actors to exchange information and knowledge. This strategy is implemented with the creation of three strands, namely Knowledge Exchange Formats (which are described in this deliverable), Discussion Formats (described in D2.1 [13]), and a Research Integration Board (described in D2.6 [14]) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Firelogue Support Dimension.

The principal goal of the **Knowledge Exchange Formats** will be to promote and develop joint exchange activities for the EU fire projects, to facilitate their interaction among them and with other relevant EU and non-EU initiatives, as well as with the Break-out Group (BG) and Working Group (WG) actors and the broader wildfire community. The exchange formats will be either formal or informal and encompass webinar programs, network exchange events as part of international conferences, links with trainings and exercises such as MODEX, as well as impact and outreach activities. The aim of the Knowledge Exchange Formats will be to share lessons learnt and best practices, relevant for the execution of the projects, to provide an opportunity for the projects to gather user requirements for the development of the innovative solutions, and to maximise the impact of their project outcomes.

1.2 Objectives

The principal objective of this deliverable is to **provide and define a set of Knowledge Exchange Formats as forms of cooperation, cross-fertilisation and networking among the EU fire projects from the Firelogue network.**

The performance of these interexchange activities requires orderly communication with representatives of the EU fire projects that also need to be well aligned with the rest of interactive activities planned in Firelogue. Because of that, specific objectives of this deliverable are:

- Set a proper framework for the implementation of Knowledge Exchange Formats that fits the already defined strategic and tactical interaction groups (i.e., BG and WG) ensuring

complementarity with other interaction activities from the Firelogue Support Dimension (i.e., Discussion Formats and Research Integration Board).

- Draw an approximate timeline to implement the Knowledge Exchange Formats throughout the Firelogue lifetime.
- Anticipate a contingency plan to manage the risk of underachieving the main objective.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable is composed of the following main chapters:

- Introduction: provides the overall context for the implementation of Knowledge Exchange Formats in line with other activities envisaged within the “Support Dimension” of Firelogue.
- Framework for the design of Knowledge Exchange Formats: sets the overall implementation strategy...,
- Knowledge Exchange Formats: classifies and describes the Knowledge Exchange Formats to be implemented during the project; proposes a way to keep track of the activities carried out as part of them; draws an approximate timeline for their implementation; and defines some contingency measures to avoid underachievement.
- Conclusions: the last chapter draws the conclusions and next steps throughout the project that will be reported in the next deliverable on the design of Knowledge Exchange Formats – D2.8 and D2.9.

2 Framework for the design of Knowledge Exchange Formats

Firelogue approaches the WFRM from a multidisciplinary perspective counting on the contribution from experts coming from a variety of fields such as social science, ecology, economy, or industry, and making them interact towards innovative management solutions to deal with the current context of increased fire risk. To do this, the project creates, implements and dynamizes a series of Knowledge Exchange Formats that facilitate and promote the cooperation among the EU fire projects, and likewise making it extensive to the broader WFRM community. For an efficient knowledge transfer among all these actors, Firelogue needs to maintain continued dialogue with the projects, leading to the identification of common needs and challenges according to their objectives and fields of work.

Knowledge Exchange Formats are a form of interaction that coexist with the **Discussion Formats** [13] and the **Research Integration Board** [14] within the Support Dimension of Firelogue (see section 1.1). The implementation of these three interactive strands requires an effective communication strategy that provides orderly and continuing means of coordination. The challenge in implementing this Support Dimension appropriately is to exploit the wealth of knowledge and developments made by the EU fire projects without overburdening them with massive communications and requests (specially the project coordinators). To achieve this, the interaction activities taking place as part of the three strands are planned at two levels –strategic and technical– allowing for the implementation of specific support actions, and so establishing communication channels that are timely, precise and tailored-made to specific representatives within each project that hold certain responsibilities and/or expertise (Figure 3):

- **Strategic level**, which is articulated by means of six **Break-out Groups (BGs)**, and cover managerial areas within each project; i.e., those setting the strategy and priorities in terms of impact assessment, research integration, or communication & dissemination of results, among others (refer to section 2.1 for a more detailed description of the six BGs). Therefore, specific communications, activities or other matters related to BG areas will only target representatives of each project who are responsible for managing these areas. The BGs were initially built during the annual Clustering event celebrated in April 2022.
- **Technical level**, which is articulated by means of the five established **Working Groups (WGs)** based on specific thematic and disciplines contributing to WFRM and the development of tangible best practices and solutions (refer to section 2.2 for a more detailed description of the five WGs). Therefore, specific communications, activities or other matters related to WGs, and their thematic will only be targeted to representatives of each project who are working on the specific thematic covered by each WG.

Dialogue spaces created within BGs and WGs would not play out independently, but they will interact one another in order to seek research integration, results transferability, and impact maximisation. For instance, this interaction may come naturally when representatives of any of the five WGs need to collect and manage the knowledge produced, implement their solutions in the scope of the case studies, or disseminate/exploit their research outcomes. Firelogue will make possible that these necessary interactive processes do not solely occur within the Consortium of each project, but among the different projects, hence enriching the wealth of knowledge and developments made by the benchmarking projects in the WFRM domain.

Discussion Formats, Knowledge Exchange Formats and the Research Integration Board correspond to the specific activities, actions as well as events' participation that can arise within the scope of the BGs and WGs. The current deliverable focuses on the design of Knowledge Exchange Formats. The plans for the co-creation of certain knowledge Exchange activities and actions, as well as joint participation in events, can be made within the scope of BGs and WGs.

While it is the primary purpose to articulate the interaction with the EU fire projects through BGs and WGs, it is worth mentioning that this interaction may happen through **other informal or spontaneous meetings**, as well as through **other planned activities** aimed to meet new needs that may arise during the projects' lifetime.

Figure 3. Firelogue strategic and technical levels articulated by means of the Working Groups (WGs) and Break-out groups (BGs), respectively.

2.1 Break-out Groups

The BGs are listed and described below:

- **Impact Assessment (towards Green Deal 2030 targets):** Revision of the achievability of the 2030 targets, definition of expected impacts and KPIs, and understand each project's impact assessment methodology.
- **Research Integration (Fuel Maps, Fire Event database, others):** Development of a European Fuel Map and of a wildfire events data base. In addition, aspects of taxonomy and wildfire risk and danger concepts were addressed.
- **Knowledge Management on research results and WFRM practices:** Collection and management of knowledge (research results, WFRM practices) to keep an overview of the initiatives/projects currently running and connect target experts. At the same time, it aims to the identification of the main audience and communication channels for better knowledge exchange actions.
- **Case study collaboration and exchange:** Identification of projects' plans in terms of case study deployment and opportunities for co-participation, exchange, and cross-fertilisation, with partners from one project attending other projects' case study demonstrations sites as observers, tech providers or participants.

- **(Technical) exploitation | legacy uptake:** Identification of challenges for the technical exploitation of the products/services that will come out from the projects (i.e., IAs and others). At the same time, the BG aims to analyse main legacy uptake gaps and the engagement and involvement level of end-users.
- **Communication & Dissemination incl. Joint Events:** Assess the importance and versatility across communication and dissemination channels to effectively impact the targeted audience that are ultimately aimed to provide the European Commission and the WFRM stakeholders with tangible solutions.

The BGs were created in the frame of the WFRM Clustering Event organised by Firelogue for the European Commission (Research Executive Agency), which took place digitally on 5th and 6th of April with the following aims:

- Discuss the key priorities for cooperation;
- ensure coherence and complementarity between the demonstration activities;
- harmonise communication activities between projects and outreach strategies towards the science-policy-practice communities;
- and increase multi-level coordination at Work Package level.

The event targeted the research and development projects in the field of WFRM as well as the WFRM community with no explicit research and development focus. As part of the event registration, participants were asked to select the BG which was more aligned with their role in the projects, to engage the BG discussions that happened during the second day of the event. For a thorough description of the Clustering event refer to deliverable D2.1 about Conceptualisation of discussion formats [13].

Each BGs is coordinated by a member of the Firelogue Consortium, that was responsible to bring up relevant aspects to discuss the strategic areas covered by each BG and ensure high level of engagement from the project representatives. The Clustering event set the ground to kick-off relevant discussions about several topics and to define the next steps for the upcoming meetings. The Clustering event will be organised on an annual basis with the support of the EC, and this will be an opportunity for the BG groups to meet together again; however, some BG groups have set up follow-up additional meetings after the Clustering event attending to special coordination needs. Examples of this are the Communication & Dissemination BG, that has been actively coordinating some social media activities created under the hashtag #EUFireProjectsUnited; the Impact Assessment BG, that is collecting the challenges of the projects to address the Green Deal expected impacts and facilitating the definition of targets, indicators, scale; the Case Study collaboration BG, that is gathering information about the case study implementation of all the projects and providing an opportunity for co-participation, exchange and cross-fertilisation, with partners from one project attending other others projects' case study demonstrations.

2.2 Working Groups

Firelogue establishes five sectorial WGs on (1) Ecology/environment, (2) Societal aspects, (3) Infrastructures, (4) Insurance, and (5) Civil Protection. Their mission will be to foster transdisciplinary dialogues to review and analyse existing WFRM approaches, and innovations suggested by their members and other activities in the broader WFRM community. To ensure structured discussions and facilitate cross-working group exchange, WGs will work along four horizontal thematic strands, reflecting the main policy aspects (Socioeconomic aspects, Climate Change Mitigation & Adaptation) and facilitators (Technology, Earth Observation) in WFRM (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Firelogue Working Groups (WGs) and Thematic Strands

WGs are led by Firelogue Consortium members with a composite of representatives from the EU fire projects as well as other invited experts. Up to date (M12 – October 2022) the WGs have not yet been constituted, although communications have been established with the project coordinators to explain their objectives, plans, and also to request the contact of representatives within their projects with the expertise to join each thematic WG. In parallel, WG leaders are preparing a Concept note with specifications on their WG implementation and the identification of relevant topics for discussion. The Concept note will be distributed among the project representatives once they have been proposed by their project coordinators. Once the WG are fully constituted, an email list will be created for regular communications and meeting agenda.

A thorough description of the implementation of the Working Groups will be provided in deliverable in D4.3 about Set-up of WGs [17].

3 Knowledge Exchange Formats

The EU fire projects aim at contributing with improved research knowledge, products, technical solutions, and services, some of them in compliance with the European Green Deal goals, and more generally with the challenges resulting from the increased risk of wildfires around the globe. To help them achieving this, Firelogue aims to define a set of Knowledge Exchange Formats, which consist of a variety of joint activities, actions, and participation in events. This can be understood as a means of collaboration among the projects that sets the grounds to empower and reinforce their integrated WFRM strategies and maximize the impact of their project outcomes. BGs and WGs can provide the space to discuss and plan and prepare the conduction of these activities resulting from relevant topics identified in the scope of their discussions.

Figure 5 displays the Knowledge Exchange Formats, which have been divided into three distinct categories: **webinars**, **networking events**, and **training and demonstration exercises**. Some examples of representative activities for each format are listed too. All these examples are in a certain way formal, since they are carried out within the framework of organized meetings or events, either by the projects themselves or by entities outside of them, which require some planning in terms of participation.

As mentioned before, BGs and WGs can provide the space to set up these activities, where projects might follow up with dedicated discussions occurring in a more informal way to convey their coordinated work, or to agree on further common actions. In addition to this, this may lead to bilateral meetings among two specific projects whose participation in those activities have allowed them to identify new paths for cooperation that they would like to continue to explore.

Figure 5. Categorisation of Knowledge Exchange Formats.

3.1 Webinars

Firelogue wants to promote webinar initiatives, that are an online space where the projects can convey and share with a wider audience the progress made in terms of innovative developments and novel knowledge. This is also an opportunity to discuss the main challenges identified in the WFRM domain, demonstrate the linkages with their solutions proposed, and get further feedback from the webinar audience. The target audience is composed of fire managers, researchers, as well as delegates from other EU projects and other people with a strong interest in the field of WFRM. Some examples of webinars are:

- **Project presentations and discussions** to explain their objectives, methodologies, developments, or research outcomes. The purpose of these webinar can be diverse: to present the global objectives, methodologies, or research outcomes; to showcase the features and functionalities available in the technological solutions while providing insight into their practical use by end-user's; or to generate discussions around current issues, such as recent wildfires causing major impacts across Europe and the world, the release of recent European policies, or to analyse certain practices for fire prevention.
- **World Café** is a working method in which a particular topic related to WFRM is being address by discussing in small table groups. To do so, an online platform (e.g., Zoom) will be used to carry out sub-topic discussions while dividing into different breakout rooms. Hence, there will be many rooms as sub-topics to be discussed. For example, a 60-minute workshop can be proposed with 3 different breakout rooms of 20 minutes each, in which all the participants will

have to move through each room and the last 20 minutes will return to the main room with all the participants to carry out a debriefing and reach some conclusions. Three main roles are required to conduct this method: the main facilitator, who will welcome all participants in the main room, explain how the workshop will proceed before dividing the session into different breakout rooms; one moderator to drive the session within each breakout room; and a notetaker to collect everything that is discussed in each breakout room.

3.2 Networking events

Firelogue encourages and facilitates the joint participation in networking spaces such as conferences, congresses, or other events in order to share, and disseminate their projects experiences, priorities, and get the feedback from the audience. Participation formats in such events can be mainly workshops or roundtable/panel discussions:

- **Workshops** are interactive spaces that include participatory methods to engage attendees with the information being presented. They are designed for situations that require input and consensus and, thus, have a specific, action-oriented purpose, and aim to generate concrete answers to specific problems. Organising workshops through the Firelogue project is a chance to interactively share and discuss about topics involving the WFRM community as well as to learn new skills and develop new minded routes on them. Due to this, it is seen as a good opportunity to involve a wide variety of technical, managerial, and scientific profiles. As an example, Firelogue participated in Firelinks WG1 meeting in May 2022 to discuss the topic “Fire occurrence, dynamics and prevention”.
- **Round table/Panel discussions** are organized conversations with one moderator and a selective panel of speakers that bring a variety of perspectives to a subject. Moderators briefly introduce the topic they wish to explore and then lead a discussion to gather input and facilitate the exchange of ideas among the speakers. As an example, Firelogue organised a Round table discussion embedded into the Fire Ecology Across Boundaries conference [11], in October 2022 in Florence to discuss the topic “Future wildfire risk scenarios addressing the expected impacts by the Green Deal related to building resilience into European landscapes”.

3.3 Trainings and demonstration exercises

Joint participation in training and demonstration exercises provides an excellent opportunity for co-participation, exchange and cross-fertilisation among projects while deploying, testing, and validating their innovative technical or non-technical solutions in the scope of practical scenarios. This can happen in the form of case study collaboration or training programs.

- **Case study collaboration** serves to facilitate that partners from one project can attend other projects’ case study demonstration sites (e.g., pilots, Living Labs, simulations...) as observers, technical providers, or participants. This way they can support other project case studies by proving technologies that might be missing, giving insight on how to enhance the performance of the demonstrations, or simply giving feedback from the position of stakeholder in the WFRM domain. The BG on case study collaboration sets the discussion to make this Knowledge

Exchange Format happen. Case study demonstrations are internal activities organised within the scope of the EU fire projects.

- **Training programs** will be encouraged as a primary source of best practices where the projects will be able to directly interact with a pool of potential end-users for the identification of requirements and test their solutions. Training can be internal activities organised within the scope of the EU fire projects or external activities organised by institutions, organisations, such as the Directorate-General for European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations (DG-ECHO), that organises the MODEX full-scale training exercise [12].

3.4 Activity tracking

A Knowledge Exchange activity tracking has been created in close coordination between WP2 "Stakeholder engagement and Knowledge exchange for the Support Dimension" and WP6 "Dissemination and insight upscaling". While WP6 leaders created an initial communication tracking template to keep track of all the communication and dissemination activities that will be conducted during the Firelogue project, the contribution of WP2 has broadened the scope of that template to likewise incorporate the activities conducted under the three strands that compose the Support Dimension of Firelogue: Discussion Formats, Knowledge Exchange Formats and Research Integration Board. This will allow the Consortium to keep track of all the activities that contribute to fulfil the essential scope of the project to facilitate and promote the flow of knowledge among the WFRM community.

The resulting activity tracking template (Figure 6) describes the main objectives and outputs for the activities and events promoted by Firelogue, including the expected impacts, objectives, and outputs of each initiative together with the corresponding date and location, and the involved stakeholders. As for the Knowledge Exchange Formats, only the formal formats will be entered in the activity tracking form, as it is pointless keeping track of every single meeting. For instance, in case of joint participation in a Conference, the event itself will be reported, but not the preparatory meetings or follow up discussions.

REPORT – FEEDBACK ON DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES / Events						
REPORTED DATE	PARTNER	Interaction formats	TITLE OF EVENT	DATE(S) & LOCATION OF ACTIVITY	OBJECTIVES OF ACTIVITY/MAIN OUTPUTS	IAs attend
19.11.2021	FHG	Meetings with the EC - Clustering Event	UN SPIDER Bonn International Conference (virtual), Space-based Solutions for Disaster Management in Africa: Networks and Information, Technologies in times of crisis	17/11/2021		-
26.11.2021	FHG	Peer Review Webinars - Project presentations and discussions	Agenda de la Reunión Regional de Expertos de ONU-SPIDER y EPREDENAC para América Latina	23-25/11/2021		-
16/09/2022	FHG	Webinars - World Cafe Webinars - Others Networking events - Workshops Networking events - Roundtable / Panel discussions Networking events - Others	Wildfire Risk Management Project Clustering Event	5-6/04/2022	Connect EU-research projects in WFRM, create a space for them to get to know each other and identify areas of cooperation; identify common goals and a shared plan (Road Map) for the coming years	DRYAD FireRE SILVANI FireUrit FireLin SAFER
16/09/2022	FHG	Networking events - Project presentation	3rd International Conference on Fire Behavior and Risk	03-06/05/2022	To present Firelogue project to the WFRM communities and to connect with possible relevant stakeholders, meet representatives of the IAs	FireUrit FireRE
	FHG	Networking events - Project presentation	ARNHEM 2022 WG1 MEETING	11-12/05/2022		

Figure 6. Interaction formats integrated into the activity tracking template.

3.5 Implementation timeline

The approximate implementation timeline for the Knowledge Exchange Formats described in section 2.3 is illustrated in Figure 7. This timeline is made based on the Firelogue temporal scope, whereas it should be taken into consideration that the EU fire projects may have different implementation timelines: while the 3 IAs are more less synchronised with similar start dates and project durations, some projects are one year older (e.g., FirEURisk) and others even more (e.g., SAFERS, Firelinks). Therefore, this timeline cannot be interpreted as a calendarization of the projects' activities, but an approximation date for the realisation of the Knowledge Exchange activities in which they may be involved under the scope and the coordination of the Firelogue project.

Webinar-related formats can take place from the start of the EU fire projects. Ordinary webinars to present the projects can be performed since the very beginning so as to expose the initial objectives, milestones, and overall plans of the projects. As the projects progress and they reach their implementation phase, these webinars can be used to present research outcomes, or for technology showcase. Ordinary webinars to discuss hot topics in WFRM can be also organised from the beginning gathering fire experts from the projects' consortiums in order to demonstrate how their projects could contribute to challenges posed by the impact of current challenges or to analyse how they could contribute to the enhancement of current best practices and solutions. Finally, World café webinars can be arranged a few months after the projects start, if the projects have some experiences to relate and insight to share resulting from their projects' activity. At this stage of the project lifetime (M12 – End of First Year), no webinars have been arranged yet, though ideas for discussions in webinar formats are expected to arise from the BG and especially from the WG discussions.

The participation of the EU fire projects in networking events starts shortly after their Kick-Off. Both workshops and roundtables can be organised once the projects have shaped their objectives and defined their priorities and guidelines to implement innovative solutions. At this stage of the project lifetime (M12 – End of First Year), workshops and roundtable discussions have already taken place in the frame of international Conferences (e.g., Fire Across Boundaries in October 2022) or events organised by other projects from the network (e.g., Firelinks WG1 meeting on “Fire occurrence, dynamics and prevention” in May 2022).

Finally, knowledge exchange among projects can happen by means of training and demonstrations exercises. Projects' case studies cooperation comes during their deployment in the form of pilots, Living Labs, or others. While the IAs and FirEurisk will not carry out the deployment of their case studies until the end of the second year at the earliest [12], SAFERS will conduct their first pilots after the first year of the Firelogue project. Other project like Firelinks or Fire-In do not carry out case study deployments. Opportunities for jointly participation in trainings can be identified approximately after the first year and a half, once the projects have reached a sufficient degree of development to contribute with applied knowledge and development in the deployment of trainings, which can be organized either by the project themselves or by external parties. At this stage of the project lifetime (M12 – End of First Year), joint participation in trainings has not occurred, but discussions for future cooperation in the frame of their case study deployments (i.e., pilots, Living Labs...) have taken place in the scope of the BG on “Case study collaboration”.

The implementation of Knowledge Exchange format is presented in deliverables D2.3, D2.8, and D2.9. While the current deliverable D2.3 presents the first implementation roadmap in M12, D2.8 will report on the outcomes and possible adjustments on the roadmap resulting from the interactions with the EU fire projects and other WFRM actors in M30, whereas the final results will be presented in D2.9 by the end of the project in M48.

Figure 7. Timeline for the implementation of Knowledge Exchange Formats.

3.6 Contingency planning

Sound and efficient coordination and management is needed in order to guarantee the successful implementation of the Knowledge Exchange Formats. The responsibility to achieve this is shared among various partners of the Firelogue Consortium: BG and WG leaders, project coordinator, and stakeholder manager. On one hand, BG and WG leaders need to plan and implement engaging activities accounting for the knowledge, expertise and expectation of the EU fire projects. On the other hand, a continuous progress monitoring of the implementation of Knowledge Exchange Format will be carried out by the project coordinator, to guarantee that all the knowledge exchange formats are developed according to plan, and by the stakeholder manager, to guarantee the involvement of high-level stakeholder groups.

Along these lines, a series of contingency measures are anticipated to foresee the risks of underachievement in terms of participation:

- **EU fire projects are overburden with participatory requests**

Overbidding the EU fire projects with constant information and requests must be avoided. “How, when and what to request” should be guiding questions when establishing communication with the projects, rather than constantly sending information that may become a spam effect.

In the event that this overload situation occurs throughout the project, it is necessary to stop the trend immediately. For that, the strategic framework for the design of Knowledge Exchange Formats described in chapter 2 will be put in place so as to establish appropriate communication channels with the projects. On top of that, a short report should be elaborated with the achievements resulting from their participation in the Knowledge Exchange activities. Furthermore, the implementation timeline drew in section 3.5 should lead to create a clear calendar with the main actions in which the Firelogue will involve the participants until the end of the project. This calendar will be embedded into the future Firelogue platform.

Therefore, preventive measures to mitigate this risk should seek to motivate the EU fire projects and to make them clearly and succinctly aware of what is expected of them, so that they can organize themselves internally.

- **Knowledge Exchange activities fail to engage full representativity of stakeholders**

It is possible that some actions proposed by Firelogue do not cause the expected impact or interest on the full spectrum of stakeholder groups (see deliverable D7.2 about “Stakeholder clustering” [13]). This can be because the topics proposed are not well-tailored to their particular interest, or simply because of the effort Required to participate in these activities. For instance, a workshop on fire ecology may raise more interest for environmental organisations than for civil protection forces.

Firelogue will support the EU fire projects in managing a variety of stakeholders including representatives from other EU-funded projects, European agencies, and other international stakeholders of the WFRM community, so their knowledge is assembled during the project development.

To achieve a balanced participation of stakeholders across the multiple Knowledge Exchange activities organised during the projects, selective stakeholder groups will be targeted according to the type of Knowledge Exchange activity implemented and the number of requests addressed to specific groups will be considerably filtered, in order to keep only the essential ones for each particular type of activity. Communication actions to encourage participation in certain activities will be targeted to specific stakeholder groups, and closer communication will be followed up if necessary to seek their active participation in the proposal.

- **Lack of commitment from the representatives of EU fire projects:**

In the undesired event of low participation from EU fire project representatives, similar prevention measure will be put in place as for the case of 'EU fire projects are overburden with participatory requests'.

Notably, the preparation of a review with the main achievements resulting from their participation, which will help them understanding the positive impact of their contributions to knowledge sharing and exchange across the broad WFRM community. Moreover, a clear and simple calendarization with the expected Knowledge Exchange activities that will be carried out throughout the project lifetime, which will make that they can decide whether to prioritise these activities within their internal organisation. Providing stakeholders with a deadline can provide them with relief from overload and possibly greater involvement.

4 Conclusions

This deliverable presents a first identification and definition of Knowledge Exchange Formats that is expected to be further developed as the Firelogue activities unfold, resulting in the creation and implementation of new formats or in the evolution of formats that are already identified towards new forms of interaction among the EU fire projects. These activities should serve to empower and reinforce integrated WFRM approaches from the EU Fire projects.

Effective communication and coordination with the EU fire projects is of utmost importance for the preparation and implementation of Knowledge Exchange activities. The engagement of the EU fire projects to be able to carry out these activities is not always appointed to their coordinators, but also to the leaders of and responsible for the different areas established by each project at the strategic level (e.g., communication, research integration, impact assessment) and at the technical level (e.g., ecology, societal aspects, infrastructures...). To articulate this process, Firelogue BG and WG leaders will identify representatives of the EU fire projects holding the responsibility and expertise of their BG and WG thematic. This coordination is essential to guarantee a smooth flow of communication with the projects.

The main risks faced by the implementation of the activities stem from the low participation of EU fire project representatives. In this sense, Firelogue must endeavour to convey the benefits of participating in Knowledge Exchange activities so that the EU fire projects see it as an opportunity to empower their research and innovation approaches rather than additional load of work to commit to. The Firelogue network has ended up integrating not only the Green Deal IAs, but also other projects dealing with WFRM (current and future). That is obviously very beneficial in terms of enriching the amount and variety of knowledge transfer and exchange, but it must be taken into consideration that the scope in which the projects are developed may vary significantly: on one hand, not all the projects are synchronised such that while some projects are in an early stage of development, others are already in the implementation stage. On the other hand, the IAs share some key objectives stemming from the Green Deal call, which may differ from the objectives set in other projects. As a result, Firelogue needs to plan for Knowledge Exchange activities seeking cooperation initiatives under common objectives and developing appropriate methodologies to ensure an optimal attraction within a broad range of stakeholders.

While the scope of the current deliverable D2.3 is simply to provide and define a set of Knowledge Exchange Formats, deliverables D2.8 and D2.9 will build on the groundwork done here, incorporating potential outcomes from the implementation of Knowledge Exchange Formats, such policy recommendations, WFRM guidelines or lessons learned from actual cooperation experiences. Also, they will analyse and explore implementation pathways to eventually put into practice the technical and scientific knowledge gained and developed.

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6 Annexes

6.1 Annex I: Survey question related to Working Groups (WGs)

Please suggest one or more members of your Consortium to each WG indicating their name, email, organisation, and role in the project. *(Free text)*

Ecology / Environment:

Type here

Societal aspects:

Type here

Infrastructures:

Type here

Insurance:

Type here

Civil Protection:

Type here

Please name in the table below the main topics/questions related to the WGs and describe briefly the main intended contribution by your project. *(Free text)*

WORKING GROUP	Relevant topics	Project main contribution
Ecology / Environment	<i>Type here e.g., ecosystem services provision, climate action policies...</i>	<i>Type here</i>
Societal aspects	<i>Type here e.g., risk preparedness campaign, citizens' engagement in decision making...</i>	<i>Type here</i>
Infrastructures	<i>Type here e.g., measures for the protection of infrastructure assets,</i>	<i>Type here</i>

	<i>development of wildfire management policies...</i>	
Insurance	<i>Type here e.g., financial compensation mechanisms, novel insurance instruments...</i>	<i>Type here</i>
Civil Protection	<i>Type here e.g., new approaches to assess wildfire danger and risk, new and existing SOPs...</i>	<i>Type here</i>

What stakeholder groups (from inside your Consortium or external) do you think should ideally join these Working Groups? (Put an X mark on the blank boxes where appropriate)

PARTICIPANT	WORKING GROUPS				
	Ecology / Environment	Societal aspects	Infrastructures	Insurance	Civil Protection
Security practitioners - Commanders/ Decision-makers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Security practitioners - In-field first responders	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forest Officials	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Land/property owners/ managers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Representatives from volunteer associations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Local administrations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Researchers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Policy Makers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Representatives from the BFSI Industry	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Fire prevention and firefighting equipment suppliers	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Representatives from environmental organisations	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Representatives of the media	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Representatives from community residents	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Others (please specify):	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Others (please specify):	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Others (please specify):	<input type="checkbox"/>				

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